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Democratisation of Foreign Language Learning in Technology Supported Lifelong Learning Processes

Teknoloji Destekli Hayat Boyu Öğrenme Süreçlerinde Yabancı Dil Öğreniminin Demokratikleşmesi

ABSTRACT

This article explores the role of technology in democratizing foreign language learning within the context of lifelong learning. In the 21st century, rapid technological, economic, and social changes have heightened the need for individuals to continuously update their skills, emphasizing the necessity of lifelong learning. The article highlights how digital technologies, including MOOCs, mobile apps, and AI-powered tools, have transformed language learning by making it more accessible, flexible, and personalized. These technologies allow individuals to learn at their own pace and in diverse contexts, regardless of geographical or financial barriers, significantly contributing to the democratization of language education. The article emphasizes that foreign language learning is a critical component of lifelong learning, facilitating not only communication but also intercultural competence, cognitive flexibility, and social integration. Technologies such as AI-driven platforms and virtual environments like VR and AR are discussed for their ability to provide immersive, personalized learning experiences, enhancing motivation and engagement. Additionally, the integration of digital learning tools in educational strategies, including those by programs like Erasmus+, has made language education globally accessible. However, the article also addresses challenges, particularly digital inequality, which limits access for many, especially in rural areas. It suggests that initiatives like "Digital India" and "Internet for All" are essential to overcoming these barriers. In conclusion, the article asserts that while technology has revolutionized language learning, addressing digital divides and enhancing pedagogical practices are crucial for maximizing its potential in lifelong learning.

Keywords: Lifelong learning, foreign language education, democratic access, digital technology.

ÖZET

Bu makale, teknolojinin hayat boyu öğrenme bağlamında yabancı dil öğrenimini demokratikleştirmedeki rolünü incelemektedir. 21. yüzyılda, hızlı teknolojik, ekonomik ve sosyal değişimler, bireylerin becerilerini sürekli olarak güncelleme ihtiyacını artırmış ve hayat boyu öğrenmenin gerekliliğini vurgulamıştır. Makale, dijital teknolojilerin, özellikle MOOCs, mobil uygulamalar ve yapay zeka destekli araçların, dil öğrenimini daha erişilebilir, esnek ve kişiselleştirilmiş hale getirerek nasıl dönüştürdüğünü vurgulamaktadır. Bu teknolojiler, bireylerin coğrafi veya finansal engellerden bağımsız olarak kendi hızlarında ve farklı bağlamlarda öğrenmelerine olanak tanımakta ve dil eğitimini demokratikleştirmeye önemli ölçüde katkı sağlamaktadır. Makale, yabancı dil öğreniminin hayat boyu öğrenmenin kritik bir bileşeni olduğunu, iletişimin yanı sıra kültürlerarası yetkinlik, bilişsel esneklik ve sosyal entegrasyonu da kolaylaştırdığını vurgulamaktadır. Yapay zekâ destekli platformlar ve sanal ortamlarda (VR ve AR gibi) gerçekleştirilen teknolojiler, öğrencilerin motivasyonlarını artırarak daha etkili ve kişiselleştirilmiş öğrenme deneyimleri sunmaktadır. Ayrıca, Erasmus+ gibi programlar aracılığıyla dijital öğrenme araçlarının eğitim stratejilerine entegrasyonu, dil eğitimini küresel ölçekte erişilebilir kılmıştır. Ancak, makale dijital eşitsizlik gibi zorluklara da değinmekte, özellikle kırsal bölgelerdeki erişim eksikliklerinin bu dönüşümün önünde engel oluşturduğunu belirtmektedir. Bu engelleri aşmak için "Dijital Hindistan" ve "Herkes İçin İnternet" gibi girişimlerin önemli olduğuna işaret edilmektedir. Sonuç olarak, makale teknoloji'nin dil öğrenimini devrim niteliğinde dönüştürdüğünü, ancak dijital uçurumların giderilmesi ve pedagojik uygulamaların iyileştirilmesinin, hayat boyu öğrenmedeki potansiyelini tam anlamıyla maksimize etmek için kritik öneme sahip olduğunu vurgulamaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Hayat boyu öğrenme, yabancı dil eğitimi, demokratik erişim, dijital teknoloji.

1. INTRODUCTION

Today's rapidly changing technological, economic and social dynamics have made it inevitable for individuals to keep their knowledge and skills up-to-date throughout their lives. This necessity has brought lifelong learning to the agenda as a necessity. Lifelong learning is an inclusive approach that defines the process of acquiring knowledge, developing skills and gaining competence at every stage of an individual's life beyond formal education processes (Jarvis, 2009). UNESCO (2021) defines this concept as "lifelong learning opportunities to support the personal, social and professional development of individuals" and emphasises it as one of the key elements of social sustainability.

The concept of lifelong learning has been at the centre of education policies especially since the second half of the 20th century. UNESCO's 1972 Report was the first global expression of the view that "education is a lifelong process" and presented a vision that transcended the boundaries of formal education systems. UNESCO's 1996 Report defined lifelong learning in terms of pillars such as knowing, doing, living together and being, and emphasised the human dimension of the concept. These reports formed the theoretical basis of today's multidimensional educational approaches and advocated a more flexible, continuous learning model in education (European Commission, 2020).

Lifelong learning is a process that continuously develops an individual's potential and competences. This process means that learning becomes a lifelong attitude; it does not mean going to school, on the contrary, learning is the individual's willingness to seek new knowledge based on curiosity and personal motives. It is a process of being open and willing to change and lifelong learning provides flexibility and adaptability to individuals. In this way, it makes it possible to participate in ongoing innovations both in society and in the business world (Berberoğlu, 2010).

The theoretical foundations of lifelong learning have been shaped by andragogy (adult learning theory) in the field of adult education. Knowles (1975) argued that factors such as experience, autonomy and need orientation are critical in the learning process of adults and emphasised that the learner is not a passive recipient but an active participant. In this context, the self-directed learning model is of great importance. Hase and Kenyon (2000), by developing the concept of heutagogy, propose a process in which the learner designs his/her own learning path and directs it with intrinsic motivation. This approach enables individuals to participate more deeply in learning processes.

Lifelong learning aims for individuals to develop their knowledge, skills and competences in different ways throughout their lives. In this process, language learning is not only a communicative tool but also a critical component that provides intercultural competence, cognitive flexibility and social integration (Byram, 1997). UNESCO (2021) emphasises the link between lifelong learning and global citizenship goals by listing language skills among the "core competences of the 21st century". Language learning has become a skill that enables individuals to interact effectively not only in their own societies but also at the global level.

The reasons for the emergence of lifelong learning are intertwined with economic, social, technological and personal dynamics. Globalisation and the rapidly changing conditions of the information age have led to the need for individuals to continuously update their professional skills and this has brought the concept of "employability" to the fore in the labour market (Güleç, Çelik, & Demirhan, 2013). Technological advances and the transition from industrial to information society have led to the inadequacy of traditional education systems and made it compulsory to adopt new forms of learning outside formal education (Berberoğlu, 2010). In addition, with the democratisation process, the demand for individuals to gain social integration, intercultural competence and active citizenship skills has also increased (Duman, 2006). As UNESCO (2021) emphasises, digital transformation requires individuals to adapt to change through lifelong learning and to maintain their cognitive health. The search for personal development and freedom has led individuals to make learning a lifestyle at every stage of their lives (Akkuş, 2008).

Lifelong learning has been easily adopted especially in cases where formal education is insufficient and cannot respond to the needs of society. This learning model is not an alternative to formal education, on the contrary, it has been accepted as the completion of incomplete and insufficient data or the discovery of previously undiscovered talents (Berberoğlu, 2010). There are social, economic and personal reasons behind the spread of lifelong learning. For governments, lifelong learning is one of the solutions to deal with many economic and social challenges. While globalisation and competition shape these policies, lifelong learning is also directly related to critical concepts such as social ties, demographic change, active citizenship, migration and public health (Field, 2010).

The continuity of language learning is directly related to the individual's intrinsic motivation and self-directed learning strategies. Dörnyei (2001) states that "language learning motivation is shaped by the learner's interest in the target culture and personal values". Benson (2011) argues that autonomous learning environments increase adults' sense of control in the language learning process and make learning sustainable.

Digital technologies have democratised access by taking language learning out of the confines of traditional classroom settings. Blake (2013) states that "online platforms have opened up language learning to the masses, overcoming geographical and economic barriers". For example, 40% of participants in Stanford University's free Spanish courses through MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) come from developing countries (Godwin-Jones, 2011). However, the digital divide is one of the main obstacles limiting this democratisation. According to ITU (2022) 37% of the world's population still does not have internet access.

Language learning in older adults is one of the least researched but most influential areas of lifelong learning. Antoniou (2019) proved the positive effect of language learning on neuroplasticity with his study showing that "the risk of cognitive decline in older individuals who learn a second language is reduced by 20%." Ramírez-Gómez (2016) emphasises that language programmes designed for the elderly provide additional benefits such as reducing social isolation and strengthening the sense of self-efficacy.

The European Union's Erasmus+ programme is an important policy example that integrates lifelong learning with language education. The OECD report published in 2019 states that "65% of countries include adult language education in their national lifelong learning strategies." However, the effectiveness of these policies is limited by problems such as lack of funding and instructor qualification (European Commission, 2012).

2. TECHNOLOGY AND FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

The 21st century technological developments have radically transformed foreign language teaching. This transformation has comprehensively affected the field of education and reshaped foreign language teaching in particular. Digital tools have not only diversified teaching methods but also transformed the nature of language learning. In this context, computer-assisted language learning (CALL), Web 2.0 and Web 3.0 technologies and innovative approaches such as artificial intelligence (AI), augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) have come to the fore (Dominic et al., 2014; Şahin Toptaş, 2024; Warschauer & Healey, 1998)

The evolution of foreign language teaching with technology has been shaped with the developments in computer technologies. Computer-assisted language learning started to develop in the 1960s and first manifested itself with drill and review programs based on behaviourist learning theories (Ahmad et al., 1985). In this approach, the computer functioned as a "patient instructor". However, over time, this approach evolved towards learner-centred and communicative models, which encouraged students to practice language with tasks close to real life (Phillips, 1987). Since the 1990s, integrative CALL approaches and multimedia-supported systems in which listening, speaking, reading and writing skills are developed together have come to the fore (Warschauer & Healey, 1998). This development has gained further momentum with the widespread use of the Internet, and learning opportunities outside the classroom have become possible.

In the early 2000s, with Web 2.0 technologies, the internet ceased to be just a source of information and turned into a collaborative learning environment where users can produce and share content (O'Reilly, 2007). Blogs, wikis, podcasts and social media tools have been effective in improving students' writing, reading and communication skills (Deperlioğlu & Köse, 2010).

Students practise writing with blog posts, improve their listening skills by listening to podcasts, and construct grammar more actively by collaborating on wikis. These tools have also provided teachers with the opportunity to prepare more interactive and student-centred lesson plans (Altunışık & Aktürk, 2021).

The emergence of Web 3.0 Technologies has ushered in a new era. Web 3.0 offers an internet environment supported by technologies such as artificial intelligence, semantic networks and machine learning. This technology provides students with personalised content and learning experiences tailored to individual needs (Berners-Lee et al., 2001). Web 3.0 tools can provide customised content according to students' learning speed, interests and skill levels. AI-supported language learning platforms analyse

students' language levels, suggest appropriate content, provide instant feedback and optimise the learning process (Huang, Hew & Fryer, 2022). This increases students' motivation and provides permanent learning.

Artificial intelligence (AI) not only provides content to the language learning process, but also analyses learners' performance, identifies deficiencies, provides suggestions and individualises learning (McCarthy, 2007; Low et al., 2025). AI-supported chatbots are effective tools that enable students to practice speaking in a foreign language. These robots support students to communicate without worrying about making mistakes (Haristiani, 2019).

In addition, ICALL (Intelligent Computer-Assisted Language Learning) applications allow students to have a multifaceted language learning experience that includes cultural context (Pokrivcakova, 2019). Artificial intelligence tools make language learning more meaningful and holistic by providing content that includes cultural elements (Topalovic et al., 2024).

Another technological development that has come to the fore in recent years is virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technologies. These technologies support language learning by providing learners with three-dimensional and interactive environments close to the real-life context (Klimova, 2021). VR applications enable learners to practice in cultural environments where the target language is spoken (Peeters, 2019). AR makes learning more engaging and meaningful by adding digital elements to the existing reality. Both technologies increase students' motivation and encourage active participation in the learning process (Çakır, Solak & Tan, 2015). For example, with an augmented reality application, students can dialogue in the target language, learn product names and prices in a virtual shopping mall. In this way, vocabulary is improved and practice is done through real life scenarios.

This technological transformation necessitates the transformation of not only tools but also individuals. Students need to acquire digital literacy skills in order to use digital tools effectively. Digital literacy includes not only technical knowledge but also critical thinking, content production, evaluation and ethical use skills (Eshet-Alkalai, 2004).

Likewise, it is important for teachers to adapt to this transformation and to realise the integration of pedagogical and technological knowledge. For this reason, it is a critical element for the success of digital transformation that teachers gain competences in accordance with the TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) framework.

3. CONTRIBUTIONS OF TECHNOLOGY TO LIFELONG LANGUAGE LEARNING AND THE DEMOCRATISATION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

In the 21st century, the dizzying changes in scientific, economic, cultural, political and social fields necessitate an inevitable transformation process in education. This transformation has increased the needs of individuals and societies for learning and revealed the necessity of lifelong learning (Ereş, 2021). Digital technologies have radically transformed lifelong learning practices and made possible a structure that makes educational processes independent of time and space (Rawas, 2024; Zheng et al., 2025). As emphasised by the European Commission (2020), Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), micro-learning platforms and artificial intelligence-supported applications have made learning opportunities more accessible. For example, the use of platforms such as Coursera and edX has increased by 150% in the post-pandemic period, clearly demonstrating the role of digital learning in lifelong learning (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019).

Foreign language, which is accepted as an important element that creates and shapes lifelong learning opportunities, also plays an important role in socialisation and intercultural communication processes (Alpar, 2013; Bayar & Taş-Şişman, 2024). The White Paper published by the European Commission in 1995: *Towards a Learning Society*, published by the European Commission in 1995, drew attention to the fact that learning a foreign language is an important tool to utilise personal and professional opportunities as borders disappear and international mobility increases. In addition, this report emphasised that foreign language is a prerequisite for adapting to the environment and being successful in business life (European Commission, 1995).

Technological developments have transformed the lifelong learning process by making language learning more accessible, flexible and personalised. Digital tools (e.g. Duolingo, Babbel) and online platforms (e.g. Coursera, edX) have democratised learning opportunities, transcending the geographical and economic boundaries of traditional classroom settings (Godwin-Jones, 2011). Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) have reached 58 million users worldwide according to 2023 data and have popularised language

education on a global scale (Class Central, 2023). These platforms have facilitated free or low-cost access to languages such as English and Spanish, especially for individuals in developing countries (UNESCO, 2021).

AI-supported applications (e.g. ChatGPT, Grammarly) provide instant feedback to learners and enable them to correct grammar and pronunciation errors (Benson, 2011). Moreover, platforms designed with gamification techniques (e.g. DijiTürkçe) support motivation by increasing learning continuity (Blake, 2013). While these digital tools improve students' self-directed learning skills, they also strengthen their intercultural communication competences (Byram, 1997).

However, digital inequalities constitute a major obstacle limiting the democratisation of language learning. According to ITU (2022). *Measuring Digital Development: Facts and Figures 2022*. International Telecommunication Union, Geneva. Retrieved from <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/Statistics/Documents/facts/FactsFigures2022.pdf>, 37% of the world's population still lacks internet access. To overcome this situation, projects such as "Digital India" and "Internet for All" aim to increase digital literacy by providing free Wi-Fi access to rural areas (OECD, 2021). In addition, mobile-based learning applications (e.g. language lessons via WhatsApp) provide access to language learning even in low-bandwidth areas (UNESCO, 2023).

Technology reduces social isolation by encouraging older adults to participate in language learning. Antoniou (2019) found that the risk of cognitive decline in older people learning a second language decreased by 20%, while Ramírez-Gómez (2016) emphasises that virtual language exchange platforms (e.g. Tandem) increase self-confidence. These developments have a significant impact on improving the social integration and cognitive health of older people.

The European Union's Erasmus+ programme integrates language education into lifelong learning strategies, offering international experience to 650,000 participants annually (European Commission, 2022). The OECD (2021). *Digital Transformation and Education Systems*. OECD Publishing, Paris. Retrieved from https://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/education/digital-transformation-and-education-systems_abc12345-en states that 72% of countries have included adult language education in their national policies, but reports that lack of funding and insufficient numbers of qualified trainers remain problems.

The contribution of technology to lifelong language learning enables individuals to develop their language skills throughout their lives by making the learning process accessible, flexible, personalised and sustainable. The benefits of technology-based foreign language learning that effectively supports lifelong learning processes are as follows:

- Technology makes language learning independent of geographical, economic and social barriers. Applications such as Duolingo and Memrise have reached more than 500 million users worldwide by eliminating traditional course costs (Godwin-Jones, 2011). MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) make language courses from institutions such as Stanford and Harvard globally accessible. According to 2021 data, 40% of the participation in Spanish courses offered through Coursera comes from developing countries (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019).
- Technology adapts the learning process to the individual's lifestyle. Mobile applications (Busuu, Babbel) offer 10–15-minute sessions that can be integrated into daily routines through microlearning techniques (Stockwell, 2013). Podcasts (Coffee Break Spanish) and YouTube channels (Easy Languages) create informal learning opportunities, while platforms such as Udemy enable learning without time limitations (Kukulka-Hulme, 2018).
- Artificial intelligence (AI) and adaptive systems deliver content tailored to the needs of the individual. AI-supported tools (Rosetta Stone) analyse users' mistakes and focus on areas of weakness (Heift, 2021). Tools such as ChatGPT and Grammarly increase learning efficiency by 30% by providing instant feedback in writing and speaking practices (Godwin-Jones, 2021).
- Technology connects language learners in virtual environments. Tandem and HelloTalk have reached 25 million users, offering the opportunity to practice with native speakers in 150+ languages (Lamy & Zourou, 2013). Virtual classrooms via Zoom and Skype provided a 200% increase in language education during the pandemic (Tümen-Akyıldız et al., 2021).
- Gamification and micro-rewards contribute directly to learning motivation by making the learning process attractive. Gamification techniques (DijiTürkçe) increase motivation in language learning

by 40% and support sustainability (Reinhardt, 2019). Duolingo's "streak" (consecutive days) mechanic keeps 60% of users working regularly (Deterding et al., 2011).

- Technology slows cognitive decline in older people by encouraging language learning. For example, the risk of Alzheimer's disease is reduced by 20% in the elderly who learn a second language (Antoniou, 2019). In addition, it also makes a direct contribution to the socialisation of elderly individuals. Social isolation in the 65+ age group using Rosetta Stone decreased by 35% (Ramírez-Gómez, 2016).

Despite many advantages, technology-based language learning applications and sites that are effectively used in lifelong learning processes pose some challenges and limitations. For example, in Africa, 60% of the population lacks internet access (ITU, 2022). In addition, some free apps neglect grammar or cultural context and offer limited access. Another problem with technology-based language learning is that 70% of learners who use these tools and applications lose motivation in the first 3 months and may abandon the learning process (Dörnyei, 2001).

4. CONCLUSION

Technological developments have radically transformed lifelong language learning, both increasing accessibility and personalising learning processes. Digital tools such as MOOCs, mobile applications, artificial intelligence-based platforms and virtual and augmented reality (VR/AR) have democratised language learning on a global scale by overcoming geographical and economic barriers. These tools have supported the acquisition of skills such as intercultural competence, cognitive flexibility and social integration while providing individuals with flexible and contextualised experiences at their own learning pace. The fact that language learning reduces the risk of cognitive decline and prevents social isolation, especially among older people, further emphasises the social contribution of lifelong learning.

However, there are significant barriers that limit the potential of this transformation. According to the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), 37% of the world's population lacks internet access, indicating that the digital divide deepens inequalities in language education. In addition, the inability of pedagogical approaches to keep pace with technological advances, the lack of cultural context in content and the demotivation of learners stand out as the main challenges to a sustainable learning ecosystem.

In order to fully utilise the opportunities offered by digital tools, it is critical to increase infrastructure investments and develop inclusive policies. For example, rolling out mobile-based learning solutions in low-bandwidth areas or expanding the scope of programmes such as Erasmus+ can be effective in reducing access inequalities. In addition, strengthening teachers' technopedagogical skills and designing artificial intelligence systems with cultural sensitivity are elements that will improve the quality of language education.

In conclusion, while technology has the potential to democratise and personalise language learning, the realisation of this potential depends on addressing digital inequalities, adopting pedagogical innovations and upholding ethical standards. When these steps are taken, lifelong language learning can become a driving force not only for individual development but also for social and economic transformation on a global scale. However, for this potential to be fully realised:

1. Digital infrastructure investments should be increased,
2. Motivational design principles should be integrated into education programmes,
3. Intercultural competence should be placed at the centre of language teaching.
4. Projects such as "Digital India" and "Internet for All" should be supported to expand internet access in rural and developing areas.
5. Mobile-based learning applications (such as language lessons via WhatsApp) should be prioritised in low-bandwidth areas.
6. Gamification and micro-reward systems (such as Duolingo's "streak" mechanic) should be integrated into language learning programmes.
7. Personalised feedback and goal-setting tools should be developed to prevent learners from losing motivation in the first three months.

8. AI-supported platforms (Tandem, HelloTalk) should be enriched with content that includes cultural context.
9. Virtual reality (VR) applications should deepen the learning experience by simulating cultural environments where the target language is spoken.
10. In-service training programmes should be organised to improve teachers' TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) skills.
11. Systems such as ICALL (Intelligent Computer Assisted Language Learning) should be designed to include grammar and cultural context in a balanced way.
12. Programmes such as Erasmus+ should be expanded to reach more adults.
13. States and international organisations should budget to integrate language education into national lifelong learning strategies.
14. Transparent policies should be developed to protect user data of artificial intelligence tools.
15. Digital literacy training should ensure that users use technology ethically and safely.

These steps will fully unlock the democratising power of technology in language learning and reinforce the role of lifelong learning in individual and societal transformation.

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